

Radio-Frequency Energy-Induced Heating for hot spots with the same SAR averaged over 0.1 gram without perfusion

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Background: The specific absorption rate (SAR), which is the rate at which radio-frequency (RF) energy is absorbed per unit mass, is used for evaluating induced heating effects in human tissue at a hot spot. SAR, specifically averaged over a mass of 0.1 gram of human tissue (referred to as $SAR_{0.1g}$), serves as an input parameter in assessing the potential temperature rise (ΔT) caused by RF energy at the hot spot in some studies [1]. When direct ΔT calculation cannot be made, $SAR_{0.1g}$ is used by some researchers as a metric for comparison between the expected ΔT for hot spot of different types or geometry of implants.

In our previous work, we presented analytical solutions for estimating ΔT as a result of the SAR distribution exhibiting spherical symmetry with both uniform and Gaussian distributions [2]. It is important to note that ΔT was evaluated without influence of blood perfusion, and thus additional cooling effect. Here we aim at offering a comprehensive analysis of ΔT by examining cases where $SAR_{0.1g}$ remains constant but the spatial distribution of SAR inside and outside the averaging volume is different.

Methods:

We consider for convenience the scenario of a sphere of radius R enclosed in an infinite medium. Due to the inherent symmetry, the temperature distribution inside and outside the sphere depends solely on the radial distance r from the center, provided that the SAR distribution itself adheres to spherical symmetry.

If the inner sphere is subjected to a uniform SAR (referred to as SAR_0), and there exists no SAR contribution beyond the boundaries of the sphere, we were able to derive analytical solutions for the transient temperature changes at the center of the sphere, where the maximum ΔT occurs, [1]:

$$\Delta T(t) = \frac{\rho \cdot SAR_0}{2k} R^2 \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{4\alpha t}{\pi R^2}} e^{-\frac{R^2}{4\alpha t}} - \left(1 - 2 \frac{\alpha t}{R^2} \right) \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{R}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha = k/(\rho \cdot C)$ is the diffusivity coefficient. For $R \rightarrow \infty$, the solution is

$$\Delta T(t) = \frac{SAR_0}{c} \cdot t \quad (2)$$

This last case with $SAR_0 = SAR_{0.1g}$ is label as 'linear'.

For a SAR source with a Gaussian distribution (standard deviation of σ , b is the SAR value at the center of the Gaussian) located in an infinite medium of uniform properties:

$$SAR(x, y, z) = b e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2+z^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (4)$$

the analytical transient solution in the center, where maximum temperature occurs, is [1]:

$$\Delta T(t) = \frac{\rho b \sigma^2}{k} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{2\alpha t}{\sigma^2}}} \right) \quad (5)$$

A sphere with a radius $R_{0.1g} = 2.88$ mm ($S_{R_{0.1g}}$) includes a tissue weighing of 0.1 g. We calculated the transient ΔT resulting from $SAR_0 = 1$ W/kg for a set of spheres with radii of 2.88, 6.2, 13, 26, and 39 mm using equation #2. The second and the third radii correspond to spheres with a tissue mass of 1, and 10 grams, respectively. For the Gaussian distribution case, we derived the transient ΔT for a set of σ ranging from 0.65 mm to 26 mm and maintained $SAR_{0.1g} = 1$ W/kg in $S_{R_{0.1g}}$. The Gaussian distribution was centered on the center of the $S_{R_{0.1g}}$ and the constant b was calculated to yield an average SAR of 1 W/kg over $S_{R_{0.1g}}$. This set of distributions aims at covering the RF power deposition scenarios due to the presence of various types of implants, from a catheter needle to an orthopedic device. All these scenarios therefore differ in the SAR spatial distribution, yet all of them yielding the same average SAR over $S_{R_{0.1g}}$.

For numerical results, we assigned tissue properties: $\rho = 1000$ kg/m³, $C = 4000$ J/kg/K, $k = 0.5$ W/m/K. These values were fixed for a normal tissue temperature of 37°C and remained constant regardless of changes in tissue temperature. The final temperature within the human tissue at the center of the sphere can be expressed as $T_{\text{tissue}}(t) = T_{\text{tissue_start}} + T_{\text{max}}(t)$, where $T_{\text{tissue_start}}$ represents the initial tissue temperature and $T_{\text{max}}(t)$ is the result of equation 2 or 5. To avoid any potential confusion, we've chosen to utilize the label ' ΔT ' commonly associated with temperature rise in human tissue, which is used in the result figures in place of $T_{\text{max}}(t)$.

Results and Discussion:

In the absence of perfusion considerations, this study presents a conservative but analytical assessment of ΔT . It covers hotspots with both uniform and Gaussian-shaped SAR distributions, with $SAR_{0.1g} = 1$ W/kg (refer to Figure 1). Notably, for the Gaussian distributions with σ less than 1.625 mm, power deposition mainly occurred within the sub-sphere and b significantly depends on σ and the smaller σ , the larger b . Transient results for uniform $SAR_0 = 0.1$ W/kg are shown in Figure 2.

Transient results for various σ values in the Gaussian distribution are shown in Figure 3. When $\sigma > 2 \cdot R_{0.1g}$, power deposition tends to be uniform across the sub-sphere and remains relatively unaffected by σ . On the contrary, ΔT is significantly affected by σ over the entire studied range. When $\sigma > 0.45 \cdot R_{0.1g}$, smaller σ values correspond to smaller ΔT values and shorter times ($\tau_{0.632}$) needed for the transient ΔT to reach 0.632 times the asymptotic value $(1-e^{-1}) \cdot \Delta T(t \rightarrow \infty)$, as indicated in Table 1.

At the maximum SAR location, diffusion acts as cooling. The more uniform was the SAR profile, the less there was diffusion cooling and the closer b was to $SAR_{0.1g}$. For the sharpest profile, i.e., $\sigma=0.65$ mm, $b=22.9$ is significantly larger than $SAR_{0.1g}$. For $t < 1.5$ min Gaussian distributions with $\sigma \leq 0.45 \cdot R_{0.1g}$ resulted in higher ΔT than the 'linear' scenario in which $SAR_0 = SAR_{0.1g}$. Still for $\sigma \leq 0.45 \cdot R_{0.1g}$, the smaller was σ , the larger was $\Delta T(t=15 \text{ min})$ and $\Delta T(t \rightarrow \infty)$. However, the balance between the temperature increase due to RF energy power deposition and diffusion cooling appeared rather quickly. As a result $\tau_{0.632}$ was smaller than 1.5 min and the increase of ΔT for such profiles was very small for $t > 1.5$ min. The ratio of ΔT for the linear case to the ratio of ΔT for $\sigma=1.625$ mm was 20.4 at $t=15$ min.

For the entire range of investigated values of σ , the smaller was σ , the shorter $\tau_{0.632}$.

The ratio ΔT at $t=15$ minutes for the linear case and a sphere with $R = 39$ mm is only 1.017. Therefore, for $t \leq 15$ minutes under the assessed RF exposure conditions, the impact of SAR distribution outside sphere with $R = 39$ mm (assuming the RF exposure remains within the level of the assessed sphere) is negligible. Such conditions usually occur when human tissues come into contact with active or passive implants with a conductive element, the geometry of which is linear or spherical, for example, cylindrical or spherical AIMD electrodes. On the contrary, consider a configuration with a set of electrodes located on the inner surface of a ring with a diameter of less than 15 mm. In this scenario, a significant power deposition near other electrodes makes Equation 5 unsuitable for estimating ΔT .

Neglecting diffusion in general leads to a linear increase in temperature. The 'linear' scenario, in which $SAR_0 = SAR_{0.1g}$, represents the most critical situation for $t > 1.5$ min assuming no other hotspot is closer than 39mm to the hotspot under assessment. Lack of consideration of the SAR outside of the considered spheres results in an underestimation of the true temperature. Yet if the next SAR hotspot is sufficiently far, as shown in our study, its effect can be negligible so that hotspots can be analyzed individually.

Conclusion:

We have obtained analytical results on the effect of the SAR distribution on the conservatively estimated ΔT in different RF exposure scenarios.

Key results in our study, which did not take into account the effects of blood perfusion, are:

- (i) Using $SAR_{0.1g}$ without consideration of the distribution of SAR within and outside the enclosed volume cannot be a reliable tool for temperature rise estimation (ΔT).
- (ii) For Gaussian distributions of power deposition, we found:
 - a smaller σ leads to shorter $\tau_{0.632}$
 - two regimes: for $\sigma > 0.45 \cdot R_{0.1g}$ a smaller σ leads to smaller ΔT , but for $\sigma \leq 0.45 \cdot R_{0.1g}$ a smaller σ leads to higher ΔT at a given time, for example, $t = 15$ minutes, while maintaining the same $SAR_{0.1g}$.

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a)

b)

Figure 1. a) SAR profiles for SAR sources with different Gaussian distribution, i.e., standard deviation of σ in mm, but the same $SAR_{0.1g}=1$ W/kg for a sub-sphere with tissue mass of 0.1 g, i.e. radius of 2.88 mm, located in the center of spherical coordinate system. b) SAR profiles for SAR sources with uniform distribution and sphere radius of 2.88mm, 6.2 mm, 13 mm, 26 mm, and 39 mm.

Figure 2. Transient temperature rise at $x=y=z=0$ for a uniform SAR of 1 W/kg over different volumes.

Figure 3. Transient temperature rise at $x=y=z=0$ for SAR sources with the Gaussian distribution located in an infinite medium of homogeneous properties and $SAR_{0.1g}=1$ W/kg. Linear line was calculated as $\Delta T = \frac{SAR_{0.1g}}{c} \cdot t$.

Table 1 Transient results at $x=y=z=0$ for spheres of $R= 2.88, 6.2 \text{ mm}, 13 \text{ mm}, 26 \text{ mm}, 39 \text{ mm}$ in radius for uniform SAR of 1 W/kg , and for the Gaussian distributions

SAR distribution	$\sigma/R_{0.1g}$	Time $\tau_{0.632}$ min	$\Delta T(t=15 \text{ min})$ °C	$\Delta T(t=+\infty)$ °C
$\sigma=26 \text{ mm}$	9.030	288	0.18158	1.356957
$\sigma=13 \text{ mm}$	4.515	72	0.118368	0.342979
$\sigma=6.5 \text{ mm}$	2.257	18	0.053954	0.089567
$\sigma=4.33 \text{ mm}$	1.505	8	0.030905	0.042774
$\sigma=3.25 \text{ mm}$	1.129	4.5	0.020936	0.02656
$\sigma=2.6 \text{ mm}$	0.903	2.88	0.015956	0.019243
$\sigma=2.167 \text{ mm}$	0.752	2	0.013264	0.015477
$\sigma=1.625 \text{ mm}$	0.564	1.125	0.011024	0.012355
$\sigma=1.3 \text{ mm}$	0.451	0.73	0.010846	0.011871
$\sigma=1.083 \text{ mm}$	0.376	0.5	0.011658	0.012563
$\sigma=0.8125 \text{ mm}$	0.282	0.283	0.01478	0.015625
$\sigma=0.65 \text{ mm}$	0.226	0.183	0.018525	0.019363
Uniform $R=2.88 \text{ mm}$	-	1.05	0.00745	0.008
Uniform $R=6.2 \text{ mm}$	-	4.85	0.03013	0.038
Uniform $R=13 \text{ mm}$	-	20.65	0.096503	0.169
Uniform $R=26 \text{ mm}$	-	85	0.193171	0.676
Uniform $R=39 \text{ mm}$	-	192	0.22119	1.521
Linear	-	-	0.225	-

1. Shrivastava D. (Editor). Theory and Applications of Heat Transfer in Humans. John Wiley & Sons Ltd. ISBN:9781119127307. DOI:10.1002/9781119127420. April 27th, 2018.
2. Kozlov M, Boulant N. Analytical Evaluation of Radio-Frequency Energy-Induced Heating in a Hot Spot without perfusion, ISMRM 2022, p2632.

Synopsis

Evaluating induced temperature rise (ΔT) in human tissue at a hot spot.

Comprehensive analysis of ΔT by examining cases where $SAR_{0.1g}$ (SAR, specifically averaged over a mass of 0.1 gram of human tissue) remains constant but the spatial distribution of SAR inside and outside the averaging volume is different.

Analytical solutions were obtained for estimating ΔT as a result of the SAR distribution exhibiting spherical symmetry with both uniform and Gaussian distributions.

Using $SAR_{0.1g}$ without consideration of the distribution of SAR within and outside the enclosed volume cannot be a reliable tool for estimation of ΔT .

Impact

We have obtained analytical results on the effect of the SAR distribution on the conservatively estimated ΔT in different RF exposure scenarios.

Transient temperature rise at $x=y=z=0$ for SAR sources with the Gaussian distribution (standard deviation of σ in mm) located in an infinite medium of homogeneous properties and $SAR_{0.1g}=1$ W/kg. Linear line was calculated as $\Delta T = \frac{SAR_{0.1g}}{c} \cdot t$.

Eq #1

$$\Delta T(t) = \frac{\rho \cdot SAR_0}{2k} R^2 \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{4\alpha t}{\pi R^2}} e^{-\frac{R^2}{4\alpha t}} - \left(1 - 2 \frac{\alpha t}{R^2} \right) \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{R}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}} \right) \right)$$

$$\triangle T(t) = \frac{\rho \cdot SAR_0}{2k} R^2 \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{4\alpha t}{\pi R^2}} e^{-\frac{R^2}{4\alpha t}} - \left(1 - 2 \frac{\alpha t}{R^2} \right) \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{R}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}} \right) \right)$$

$$\alpha = k / (\rho \cdot C)$$

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$$R \rightarrow \infty$$

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Eq #2

$$\Delta T(t) = \frac{SAR_0}{C} \cdot t$$

$$\triangle T(t) = \frac{SAR_0}{C} \cdot t$$

Eq #3

$$SAR(x,y,z) = b \cdot e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2+z^2}{2\sigma^2}}$$

Eq #4

$$\Delta T(t) = \frac{\rho b \sigma^2}{k} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{2\alpha t}{\sigma^2}}} \right)$$

$$\triangle T(t) = \frac{\rho \cdot b \cdot \sigma^2}{k} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{2 \cdot \alpha \cdot t}{\sigma^2}}} \right)$$

$$(1 - e^{-1}) \cdot \Delta T(t \rightarrow \infty)$$

$$(1 - e^{-1}) \cdot \triangle T(t \rightarrow \infty)$$

Equation from ISMRM 2022.

Eq #1

$$\nabla^2 T + \rho SAR = \rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t}$$

Eq #2

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \rho SAR_0 = 0$$

Eq #3

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) = 0$$

Eq #4

$$T_{\max} = \frac{\rho SAR_0}{2kR^2}$$

Eq #5

$$T_{\max} = \frac{\rho SAR_0}{2kR^2} \cdot \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{4\alpha t}{\pi R^2}} \right) e^{-\frac{R^2}{4\alpha t}} - \left(1 - 2\sqrt{\frac{\alpha t}{R^2}} \right) \cdot \text{erf} \left(\frac{R}{2\sqrt{\alpha t}} \right)$$

Eq#6

$$T_{\max} = \frac{\rho b \sigma^2}{k} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{2\alpha t}{\sigma^2}}} \right)$$

Eq#7

$$t_{0.632} = (e^2 - 1) \frac{\sigma^2}{2\alpha}$$